

Stability of Lyophobic Colloids. Part-XIX. Applicability of the various modifications of Wetham's rule for the hydrophobic sols in a medium of varying dielectric constants of the dispersing medium

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The applicability of the relations proposed by Verwey and Overbeek and by S. Ghosh, *et al.* for the precipitation value of mono-, bi-, and trivalent coagulating ions have been examined here for the positively charged hydrous ferric oxide sols obtained by varied methods and containing different amounts of free peptilising hydrogen ions and at the varying dielectric constants of the dispersing medium. It has been concluded that the former relation having a number of theoretical evolutions restricts its applicability over large range of coagulation studies. The relations suggested by Ghosh, *et al.* represents the data more precisely but has a limited application in as much as it does not consider the specific effect of ions and of the dispersed material, which factors have been also ignored by Verwey and Overbeek. However, it appears from our experimental data that the ratio of the precipitating values generally diminish with the decreasing stability of the sols of hydrous ferric oxide studied here.

Schulze and Hardy¹ showed the importance of valency of the coagulating ions for a lyophobic sol and Whetham² proposed a relation for the precipitation values of the ions with their valencies. This was based on the greater probability of charge neutralisation of the colloidal units by the highervalent oppositely charged ions. However, these simple relations are hardly found to represent the data precisely.

S. Ghosh *et al.*³ developed a relation on the consideration of the electrical interaction of the coagulating ions with those in the double layer shielding the colloidal units. They have proposed that if such factors as specific adsorption of the coagulating ions or that of similarly charged ions available from the electrolyte added do not complicate the process, the precipitation values may be expressed by the relation $(1 : \frac{1}{2} < : \frac{1}{3} <^n)$ where ' α ' is defined as $e \cdot Qe / \epsilon r k T$, ' Q ' being the electrical charge on the colloidal particles, ' r ' the thickness of the double layer, ' e ' the electronic charge, ' ϵ ' the dielectric constant, ' k ' the boltzman constant and ' T ' the absolute temperature. If ' n_0 ' is the number of ions added for charge neutralisation, the actual number ' n ' effective in the process of charge neutralisation is given by

$$n = n_0 e^{-\frac{(A-Qe/\epsilon r)}{kT}} \quad (1)$$

where ' A ' is a constant and $(A-Qe/\epsilon r)$ is the minimum amount of energy required by the univalent coagulating ions to overcome the repulsion of the double layer. Thus, with a

1. Schulze, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1882, 25, 491; Hardy, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1899, 66, 110.
2. Whetham, *Phil. Mag.*, 1899, 48, 474.
3. cf., Chakravarty M. N., Ghosh, S. and Dhar, N. R., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 326.

decrease in the value of 'Q', the value of ' α ' approaches unity. In other words, in the limiting case the ratio becomes $(1 : \frac{1}{2} : \frac{1}{3})$.

Another analytical expression has been obtained by Verwey and Overbeek⁴ on the consideration of the total energetic interaction occurring between the double layer of colloidal dispersed units, according to which the flocculation value 'O' in millimoles comes to $(8.10^{-48} \gamma^4 / A^2 v^6)$ where 'A' stands for the van der Waal's constant, 'v' the valency of the coagulating ions and the value of ' γ ' is given by the factor $(ez/2 - 1)/(ez/2 + 1)$ in which $z = (\Psi_0 e v / kT)$ and ' Ψ_0 ', the surface potential, while 'k', 'v', 'e' and 'T' have their usual meanings. Further, according to Verwey and Overbeek, the number of flocculating ions per unit volume 'n' is given as,

$$n = 107 \epsilon^3 k^3 T^3 \gamma^4 / A^2 (ze)^6 \quad (2)$$

where all terms have their usual significance. For large values of 'Z' or high double layer potential the factor (γ^4) approaches unity. For such a case the precipitation values of mono-, bi-, and trivalent ions are in the ratio of $1 : (1/2)^6 : (1/3)^6$ or $100 : 1.6 : 0.13$. Again, it can be seen that for a low value of surface potential, the relation may appear as $1 : (1/2)^6 : (1/3)^6$. Thus, on a rigorous test of this relation the ratios of the precipitation values will be found to lie between two limiting values.

In our previous communications we have investigated the various factors affecting the stability of a sol such as dielectric constant, the activation energy, steric factor, adsorption of similarly and oppositely charged ion, the time of coagulation and also the applicability of various relations proposed by different workers. The present work is an attempt to verify the applicability of the two modifications of Whetham's rule stated above, for a number of hydrophobic sols of hydrous ferric oxide of varying properties with special reference to the pH, and dielectric constant of the dispersing medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

We have studied here samples of the hydrous ferric oxide sols prepared by Pean et Gilles, Graham and Krecke's method. Further, three samples of the sols obtained by each method were prepared of varying pH values, i.e., 2.2, 3.6 and 4.5. These sol samples were labelled as A₁, A₂, A₃, B₁, B₂, B₃ and C₁, C₂, C₃ respectively as containing varying amounts of free peptising agents. The purity of each sol sample was estimated by the ratio of the Fe/Cl⁻ present in a particular sol and these were found to be 3.76, 11.63, 19.69 and 5.6, 17.06, 34.13 for the sol samples B₁, B₂, B₃ and C₁, C₂, C₃ respectively. In other words, the purities of the sol here give directly the amount of total chloride ion present in the system. The purity of the sample A₁, A₂, A₃ have not been recorded here as these sols were peptised by acetic acid and in that case the estimation of total acetate ion is rather uncertain. It is well known that the free peptising and coagulating ions have a marked effect on the stability of a sol. These have been also investigated here with the sols of varying purities and pH. It has been observed that purer sol sample shows lesser stability and vice versa. The time of complete coagulation was noted at a constant temperature of $(30 \pm 0.01)^\circ$ for mono-, bi-, and trivalent precipitating ions at varying values

4. Verwey E. J. and Overbeek, J. Th., "Theory of the stability of Lyophobic colloids", Amsterdam (1946).

of the dielectric constant of the dispersing medium, which was altered by mixing sufficiently inert organic non-electrolytes as dioxane and formamide. Further details of the experiments undertaken have already been described in our previous communications⁵. The precipitation values were resolved graphically for the various intervals of the times of coagulation viz., one hour, two hours and also for infinite time of coagulation. These values were expressed in the terms of the active masses of the respective ions and that one obtained for monovalent precipitating ion was taken to be 100 and corresponding values for di- and tri-valent precipitating ions were calculated. The values of α_1 (di/mono) and α_2 (tri/di) of the relation of Ghosh *et al* have been reported here in the table (I) for different dielectric constants of the dispersing medium for infinite time of coagulation. The tables II to IV summarises the values of the factor ' α ' for the other sol samples at the various intervals of the times of coagulation and also for the varying values of the dielectric constants of the dispersing medium. However, similar values of the relation of Verwey and Overbeek viz., ' n_1 ' (di/mono) and ' n_2 ' (tri/di) have been also obtained and these are reproduced here in tables V to VII for the similar conditions noted above.

TABLE I

Precipitation values for the sol sample 'A₁' at the infinite time of coagulation.

Dielectric Constant Values	Precipitation values for			values of	
	Potassium chloride	Potassium sulphate	Potassium ferricyanide.	α_1 (di/mono)	α_2 (tri/di)
41.71	100	1.34	0.0178	0.0268	0.0175
50.52	100	1.30	0.0165	0.0260	0.0182
59.24	100	1.23	0.0154	0.0246	0.0187
67.98	100	1.18	0.0148	0.0236	0.0190
71.19	100	1.08	0.0140	0.0215	0.0195
76.76	100	1.00	0.0133	0.0200	0.0200
77.32	100	0.90	0.0125	0.0180	0.0205
77.92	100	0.82	0.0116	0.0164	0.0212
79.29	100	0.76	0.0110	0.0152	0.0217
80.88	100	0.68	0.0099	0.0135	0.0220
82.54	100	0.59	0.0088	0.0118	0.0224

TABLE II

Values of α_1 and α_2 at varying times of coagulation for sol samples 'A'.

Dielectric constant values	Sol Sample							
	A ₁		A ₂		A ₂		A ₃	
	One Hour		Two Hours		Infinite time of coagulation		α_1	α_2
41.71	0.125	0.0432	0.090	0.0866	0.028	0.0200	0.033	0.0234
50.52	.115	.0416	.084	.0875	.027	.0206	.032	.0238
59.24	.108	.0400	.078	.0861	.026	.0210	.031	.0242
67.98	.098	.0392	.072	.0850	.025	.0216	.029	.0248
71.19	.088	.0375	.068	.0840	.024	.0222	.028	.0251
76.76	.080	.0323	.065	.0824	.023	.0230	.026	.0260
77.32	.072	.0295	.060	.0800	.021	.0235	.025	.0256
77.92	.064	.0271	.056	.0770	.020	.0240	.024	.0253
79.29	.056	.0222	.053	.0736	.019	.0245	.022	.0250
80.88	.048	.0175	.050	.0720	.018	.2500	.021	.0247
82.54	.040	.0135	.048	.0688	.017	.0256	.021	.0244

5. Nand K. C. and Ghosh, S., *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. India*, Part III, 34A, 1964.

6. Nand K. C. and Ghosh, S., *Physico. Chem. Soc. of Japan*, 1963, 33, 32.

TABLE III

Values of α_1 and α_2 for sol sample 'B' at the infinite time of coagulation.

Dielectric constant values.	Sol Samples					
	B_1		B_2		B_3	
	α_1	α_2	α_1	α_2	α_1	α_2
41.71	0.0294	0.0200	0.0320	0.0230	0.0358	0.0250
50.52	.0270	.0209	.0306	.0235	.0342	.0255
59.24	.0258	.0211	.0290	.0240	.0330	.0260
67.98	.0248	.0214	.0282	.0244	.0315	.0266
71.19	.0235	.0219	.0265	.0243	.0300	.0270
76.76	.0220	.0220	.0250	.0250	.0280	.0280
77.32	.0210	.0223	.0235	.0255	.0261	.0289
77.92	.0200	.0225	.0220	.0260	.0250	.0295
79.29	.0180	.0227	.0210	.0264	.0235	.0299
80.88	.0170	.0230	.0200	.0270	.0222	.0304
82.54	.0160	.0234	.0188	.0290	.0210	.0311

TABLE IV

Values of α_1 and α_2 for sol sample 'C' at the infinite time of coagulation.

Dielectric constant values	Sol Samples					
	C_1		C_2		C_3	
	α_1	α_2	α_1	α_2	α_1	α_2
41.71	0.0275	0.0275	0.0318	0.0265	0.0343	0.0306
50.52	0.0265	0.0265	0.0302	0.0272	0.0336	0.0312
59.24	0.0250	0.0250	0.0295	0.0275	0.0310	0.0328
67.98	0.0232	0.0232	0.0270	0.0285	0.0290	0.0338
71.19	0.0220	0.0220	0.0250	0.0294	0.0274	0.0350
76.76	0.0240	0.0240	0.0280	0.0280	0.0320	0.0320
77.32	0.0262	0.0230	0.0210	0.0264	0.0358	0.0305
77.92	0.0246	0.0235	0.0288	0.0274	0.0342	0.0310
79.29	0.0230	0.0243	0.0270	0.0288	0.0332	0.0315
80.88	0.0222	0.0247	0.0250	0.0298	0.0304	0.0326
82.54	0.0200	0.0252	0.0230	0.0307	0.0285	0.0337

TABLE V

Values ' n_1 ' and ' n_2 ' at the varying times of coagulation for sol sample A_1 , A_2 & A_3 .

Dielectric Constant Values	Sol Samples									
	A_1		A_1		A_1		A_2		A_3	
	One hour		Two hour		Infinite times of coagulation					
	n_1	n_2	n_1	n_2	n_1	n_2	n_1	n_2	n_1	n_2
41.71	4.01	6.90	4.43	8.40	6.22	10.40	6.15	10.35	5.90	9.99
50.52	4.13	6.82	4.44	8.42	6.23	10.50	6.20	10.34	5.98	9.97
59.24	4.20	6.87	4.68	8.80	6.35	10.02	6.23	10.35	6.02	9.95
67.98	4.30	6.91	4.79	8.85	6.41	10.69	6.32	10.22	6.10	9.88
71.19	4.50	6.86	4.90	8.87	6.53	10.50	6.38	10.14	6.18	9.81
76.76	4.64	6.80	5.06	9.01	6.64	10.40	6.44	10.05	6.23	9.75
77.32	4.79	6.80	5.20	9.40	6.79	10.27	6.56	9.98	6.35	9.90
77.92	4.91	6.76	5.48	9.50	6.93	10.26	6.62	9.95	6.41	9.80
79.29	5.10	6.70	5.56	10.20	7.04	10.22	6.71	9.97	6.51	9.88
80.88	5.48	6.51	5.80	10.61	7.20	10.07	6.70	9.94	6.57	9.80
82.54	5.64	6.40	5.97	11.30	7.46	10.11	7.96	9.88	6.60	9.84

TABLE VI

Values of ' n_1 ' and ' n_2 ' for sol sample 'B' at infinite time of coagulation.

Dielectric Constant values	Sol Samples					
	B_1		B_2		B_3	
	n_1	n_2	n_1	n_2	n_1	n_2
41.71	6.08	10.37	5.97	10.05	5.72	9.91
50.52	6.21	10.35	6.03	9.95	5.80	9.78
59.24	6.29	10.35	6.11	10.01	5.92	9.68
67.98	6.33	10.32	6.15	9.79	6.01	9.71
71.19	6.45	10.45	6.23	10.10	6.05	9.66
76.76	6.57	10.35	6.32	9.85	6.25	9.52
77.32	6.58	10.14	6.40	9.84	6.32	9.40
77.92	6.65	10.11	6.46	9.79	6.37	9.43
79.29	6.70	10.09	6.57	9.72	6.40	9.47
80.88	6.84	10.05	6.61	9.68	6.46	9.36
82.54	6.96	10.01	7.12	9.48	6.57	9.44

TABLE VII

Values of ' n_1 ' and ' n_2 ' for sol sample 'C' at the infinite time of coagulation.

Dielectric Constant values	Sol Samples					
	C_1		C_2		C_3	
	n_1	n_2	n_1	n_2	n_1	n_2
41.71	6.07	10.01	5.97	9.70	5.84	8.87
50.52	6.20	10.00	6.05	9.64	5.90	8.13
59.24	6.26	9.98	6.19	9.60	6.10	9.20
67.98	6.43	10.05	6.24	9.50	6.59	9.22
71.19	6.50	9.91	6.25	9.45	5.97	9.15
76.76	6.38	9.95	6.27	9.60	6.59	9.25
77.32	6.37	10.40	6.29	9.70	6.12	9.20
77.92	6.50	9.92	6.30	9.69	6.18	9.25
79.29	6.62	9.93	6.30	9.68	6.21	9.30
80.88	6.50	10.00	6.31	9.50	6.25	9.28
82.54	6.62	9.80	6.43	9.40	6.02	9.14

A perusal of the data recorded above reveal that :

1. A comparison of the ratios of the precipitation values for sols shows that these are more for the Acetate sol than Graham's one and it is least for Krecke's sol, when compared for the sols of same pH, that is for the sols containing the same amount of iron and the peptising hydrogen ions.

2. These ratios of the precipitation values for a sol tend to increase with the decreasing amounts of the stabilising ions and therefore with the increasing purity of the sols, achieved by progressive dialysis. However, it may be noted here that the values of ' α_1 ' and that of ' α_2 ' tend to increase with the increasing purities of the sol samples. In other words, purer sols have greater tendency to approach the limiting values of the factor ' α ' as suggested by Ghosh *et al.* and also by Verwey and Overbeek and others.

3. There is a sharp variation in the ratios of the precipitating values of mono-, bi-, and trivalent coagulating ions with the time allowed for observing complete coagula-

tion. The ratio increases when coagulation is observed for infinite time, where the process of coagulation is at its slowest and is devoid of the effect of time.

4. The ratio of the precipitation values of divalent ion to that of monovalent decreases with the increasing dielectric constant of the dispersing medium and also with the increasing stability of the sols. It is, however, seen that the ratio of the precipitation values of trivalent to divalent coagulating ions also decreases with the increasing stability for infinite time of coagulation. Further, for infinite time of observation the ratio of the precipitation values of monovalent and bivalent ions and those for the bivalent and trivalent ions are almost identical in the absence of a non-electrolyte. However, considerable deviation occurs either in the presence of non-electrolyte or when the time allowed for complete coagulation is small.

5. A consideration of the value of the factor ' π_1 ' of Verwey and Overbeek's relation shows that it tends to increase with the increasing time of coagulation and also with the increasing dielectric constant of the dispersing medium.

6. Further, these values of ' π ' are more for the stable sols when compared for the sols obtained by various methods and of varying pH.

7. The ratio of the factor ' π_2 ' increases with the increasing time of coagulation and in general these values fall with a rise in the dielectric constant of the dispersing medium. However in some cases deviations are obtained.

8. The values of the factor ' π_3 ' is maximum for sol samples 'A₁' viz., for the most stable sol, whereas it is less for the sols of lesser stability.

9. It can be concluded that in general the ratios tend to approach the limiting values of these two relations, when the stability of the sols decreases either due to a diminution in the dielectric constant of the dispersing medium or due to higher pH, or with a rise in the temperature and also when the time allowed for coagulation is decreased. Further, it is interesting to note that the values of the constants of the relation suggested by Ghosh *et al.* fall or rise in more or less a methodical way than those of the factor ' π ' of the relation of Verwey and Overbeek.

DISCUSSION

A rigorous test of any of these theoretical expressions is ordinarily not feasible because neither there is sufficient knowledge⁷ of a number of theoretical evolutions in the relation obtained by Verwey and Overbeek, nor the process of coagulation is completely devoid of any specific effect of the ions of the added electrolyte, as required for the one developed by Ghosh *et al.* Again, the limiting conditions for the verification of the either relations cannot be realised in practice because no lyophobic colloidal system can possibly exist without electric charge. However, results recorded here show that the ratio of the precipitating ions of different valences decreases with the decreasing concentration of the stabilising ion.

Let us now consider the effect of the dielectric constant of the dispersing medium on the stability of the lyophobic sols. According to the simplified relation of Verwey and

7. vide Krulyt, H. R., *Colloid Science*, Vol. I. Elsevier, (1952), p. 906.

Overbeek (vide relation—2), a decrease in the value of dielectric constant will lower the precipitation value by ϵ^3 for the precipitating ions. Our results, however, conclusively prove that the decrease in the precipitation values with the decrease in the dielectric constant of the dispersing medium is not so sharp as required by this relation. Again, it is not clear how the ratio of uni-, bi-, and polyvalent precipitating ions will vary with a change in the dielectric constant of the dispersing medium. Similarly a remarkable change in their ratios with the rates of coagulation cannot be conceived from the consideration of Verwey and Overbeek as outlined above. Further, it is significant to mention here that the value of the factor (n) in Verwey and Overbeek's relation is not at all constant.

On the other hand, according to the relation suggested by Ghosh *et al.* the precipitation values are likely to be affected by varying the dielectric constant of the dispersing medium. From the relation (1), it is evident that where the dielectric constant of the medium is decreased the number of active ions available from ' n ' will increase and the value of ' α ' in the relation of Ghosh *et al.* tends to be unity by either decrease of ' Q ' or the electric charge on the colloidal particles or by the increase in the value of ' T '.

It has been also shown by earlier workers⁸ that with the progress of the dialysis of the sol, the ratio of the precipitating concentration of uni-, bi-, and trivalent coagulating ions tends to increase and similar is the effect, when coagulations are studied at higher temperature. The values of ' α ' should however decrease with the decrease in the dielectric constant of the dispersing medium, though our results show that the values tend to increase. It appears that a decrease in the value of ' Q ' by a decrease in the dielectric constant of the dispersing medium, more than counteracts the effect of the decrease of the value of ' ϵ '. It may be equally possible that the specific effect of the ions not envisaged by Ghosh *et al.*, becomes prominent with the variation of the dielectric constant of the medium leading to sharp variations in the results.

It is seen from our data that the relation of Ghosh *et al.*, modifying the Whetham's rule is applicable when the coagulation is at its slowest, whilst, there is a sharp variation in the ratios, in the region of fast coagulation and the relation does not apply. It should be recalled here that the function of the double layer in the process of stabilisation of a colloid becomes more pronounced, when the coagulation process is at its slowest by the addition of smaller concentration of the electrolyte leading to a partial decrease of the electric charge on the colloidal particles. Hence the Smoluckowki's relation is found to fail when the coagulation is slow, where colloidal particles with residual electric charge are interacting. The relation given by Verwey and Overbeek suggests that in the region of slow coagulation the ratio of the precipitating concentration of mono-, bi-, and trivalent coagulating ions should be more towards the ratio $1 : (1/2)^6 : (1/3)^6$ than $1 : (1/2)^2 : (1/3)^2$. Similarly from the relation suggested by Ghosh *et al.*, the values of ' α ' should be smaller, when the coagulation is slow. Thus, either of the two modifications suggested for Whetham's rule indicate that there will be change in a manner which has been observed here.

Thus, an attempt to explain the effect of the dielectric constant of the dispersing medium, rate of coagulation, the electric charge or the surface potential on the colloidal

particles, the temperature of the study and the specific adsorbility of the ions render either of the theory elastic and hence, further development in this direction is indicated, which will be reported in subsequent communications.

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